

Confronting Africa's Food Crisis

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Abstract

This paper attempts to highlight Africa's role in the international system and situates Africa as one of the most natural resource rich and also the most exploited continent on the face of the earth. Despite Africa's resource-rich state, has continued to wallow in the dregs, as the epicenter of poverty, hunger, starvation as well as the characterization of conflicts, genocide, terrorism, etc. in which, Africa is hardly regarded as anything more than mere pieces of trash. It is because Africa failed to look inward for solutions to her developmental challenges. Rather, Africa embark on foreign aid and policies inimical to her strategic development and hence; the food crisis. This paper however highlights that, while the world's political economy is currently market – driven by globalization and captained by advanced economies of the north, through the instrumentality of the Bretton Woods Institutions of International Monetary Fund, World Bank, and the World Trade Organization etc. to practically peripheralize Africa on the lowest rungs in the international division of labour as primary produce exporters, market as well as capital investment, among others. Thus, the paper argued that, the peripheralization compels Africa and others, to produce what they do not consume, and consume what they do not produce, coupled with sweeping liberalization, privatization and commercialization that is trapping, lies the core of Africa's food crisis. This paper however, depended on the use of historical analysis paradigm to X – ray the historical process of the crisis.

Introduction

The extraordinary gap between the living standards of people living in the global North and those living in the global South breeds grave consequences, although it is also quite true that there are inequalities within both the North and South that must be recognized equally seriously. Thus, the inequalities noted can easily be understood primarily in context of the imperatives of the present global reality. Nonetheless, it is at least important to articulate the historical process of this unequal world, the unfolding dynamics, what Ali Mazrui calls "The African Condition", he contemplates that Africans are not the most brutalized of peoples, but are probably the most dehumanized in contemporary history, so much that the humiliation of Africans was given a Christian nod (Mazrui, 1980:30). And the generative diversity description of Africa by Greek historicity as an enigma of unpredictable people chides mother Africa as the cradle of man and

civilization (Ifidom, 2018:1), describing Africa as the breeding center of unexpected possibilities aptly consummates the African condition.

However, the ground analysis of Africa's predicament is very much linked to the rise of capitalism in Western Europe between the 15th and 19th centuries. The rise of mercantile capitalism accelerated a process of world conquest and subordination to the economic requirements of expanding European economic and military power. As a result, by the 19th and 20th centuries most of the global South had been battered and pillaged, and then, ultimately tied to Western economic centers with strings of economic and political provenance (Saul, 2006:2; Harris, 1987: 255). Corroboratively however, scholars notes that global expansion of European capitalism and imperial conquest of peripheral areas for capital accumulation is a crucial dimension of the past several centuries of world history (Palmer et al, 2001:100). Thus, a global hierarchy was formed, that would have a profound, even daring, effect on the economic and social prospects of the vast majority of the world's population, especially the African continent.

Following the complexities, however, there is the estimation of an overwhelming indications that, a growing divide between the haves and the have-nots has left increasing numbers in the Third World in dire poverty, living on less than a dollar a day. This ultimately portend that, poverty has drastically increased astronomically in billions living in abject poverty on less than \$2 a day propensity into the 21st century (Stiglitz, 2002:5). The United Nations Development Programme reports in a rather vexing note that globally, poverty and inequality seem to have degenerated in the last two decades (UNDP, 1999:2-3). Add to this fact that poverty and inequality are endemic diseases and systemic continuum in Africa is correctly reported by the World Bank thus:

Some 300 million Africans almost half the population, live on barely US. \$0.65 a day, and this number is growing relentlessly. Moreover, a severe lack of capabilities – education, health, and nutrition – among Africa's poor threatens to make poverty “dynastic”, with the descendants of the poor also remaining poor. Africa is the only region where primary enrollment rates were lower in 1995 than in 1980, and the burden of disease is drastically higher in Africa than elsewhere. Africa is not only poor, it also suffers from vast inequality in

incomes, in assets, in control over public resources, and in access to essential services, as well as pervasive insecurity. These dimensions of poverty and deprivation are worsening in many parts of the region (World Bank, 2000d as cited in Soludo, 2003: 23-24).

Whenever the so-called “African Condition” or “Africa as an enigma” comes to mind or is put into consideration, the question is, how did Africa contracted this infectious malady? And for this long? The reason is that Africa is not an island. It has to interact with the rest of the world for its own needs, for exchange of products as well as services, bound Africa to the international or global economic system. The first was the Portuguese during their trade encounter with the peoples of the Gulf of Guinea. This enterprise of the Portuguese also coincided with the activities of the Dutch at the Cape of Good Hope, and this phase set the pace for white settler concept in Africa. The Arabs visit to the coast of East Africa, which subsequently resulted in the establishment of Arab suzerainty from Muscat in Oman to Zanzibar certainly opened up Africa to participate in the global economy.

Initially, trade between Africa and the global community was mutually beneficial. However, with the discovery of the “New World” and establishment of large-scale plantation agriculture, the pendulum of relationship moved against Africa. The high mark of that era was Africans as the object of trade (slave trade). Whether it was across the Sahara Desert, the Mediterranean Sea, Indian and Atlantic Oceans, the major article of trade was, African slaves. This trade involved the massive export of Africans to work as slaves in the New World agricultural plantations. This period was however followed by one in which European nations expanded globally for raw materials for European industries, market for the manufactured goods as well as outlet for capital investment. As a result of the remarkable role played by the Industrial Revolution in Europe that called-off the slave trade, for the realization sequel to the industrial progress, the slave trade that promoted insecurity and prevented agriculture must be stopped. The bottom line was to encourage Africans to engage themselves in agricultural activities for trade.

At the initial stage of this new engagement writes Ini Udoka that it was one of interdependence peddled by market forces in which, in most cases, the Africans made profits at the expense of European merchants. The frequent loses occasioned by the European traders arising however,

from cut-throat competition among other things led to the intervention by European governments to ensure gainful business to grow their home economies partly explains the establishment of colonial rule in Africa (Udoka, 2005:37). The colonial economy was one of massive exploitation and promoted unreservedly the destruction and peripheralization of Africa's development that continues in to the present era of globalization.

This paper however hopes to interrogate the historical process of the causes of Africa's food crisis, through theoretical lenses to view this endemic crisis in the African continent.

Theoretical Framework of Africa's Development Crisis

At the dawn of independence, in the late 1950s and early 1960s by most African states, the Modernization theory was popularized by Western liberal scholars designed as the path way to the development of the newly independent African states. The summary of the modernization theory is that if Africa must develop, then it must undergo certain procedural pattern or path already adopted by the West. It is within this frame of thought that Rostow and his co-travelers believed was the only path for nations especially those in Africa to develop. Because of the divergent views of modernization theorists, at the level of policy making, African leaders and others, struggled with different strategies to overcome development challenges.

Arising from this contradiction, African scholars of different school of thought have emerged to proffer suggestions geared towards solving the problem. Notable scholars like Walter Rodney, Claude Ake, and Daniel Effiong etc. utilized the Marxian paradigm to explain the cause of underdevelopment in Africa. For these scholars, Africa's development crisis cannot be explained outside the impact of colonialism, neocolonialism and dependency. Claude Ake however, argued that the present conditions of the third world countries are not in the least comparable to the conditions of the advance economies in the earlier stages of their development. This is that the present condition of the third world according to him is the effect of the slave trade, pillage, colonialism and unequal exchange (Ake, 1995). Perhaps more compellingly Walter Rodney while contemplating the origin and trend of underdevelopment in Africa, rather bluntly opined that, Africa's development is possible only on the basis of a radical break with the global capitalist system, which has been the bane of the underdevelopment of Africa for centuries (Rodney, 1972).

Meanwhile, a school of thought strongly contends that globalization constitutes a major obstacle confronting Africa's effort to develop. This is condense to mean that the benefits of globalization are lopsided for all the regions of the world. The fact that a major feature of the

globalization process is that it cannot be ignored, the success of the development enterprise in Africa now depends on the mode of its incorporation into the global capitalist economic system. Yet, there are other scholars Mary Afolabi notes who believe that Africans should take responsibility for the present state of Africa's underdevelopment. It is articulated that Africans were the cause of their downfall; the argument is blamed on bad leadership, corruption, civil wars, military rule, authoritarianism and lack of concern for the poor, to them, have contributed more than any other thing as cause of the underdevelopment (Afolabi, 2018:58-59). The point to emphasize is that, no adequate comprehension of Africa's development crisis could be more viable without factoring the effect of three major forces; firstly, colonialism, neocolonialism and dependency; secondly, contemporary globalization, and thirdly, the role of the African ruling elite. It is to these we shall interrogate to showcase the linkages as the causes of Africa's food crisis.

Impact of Colonial Economic Policies on Africa

Truly, colonialism brought policies on roads and railways construction in the African colonies. This is meant to achieve the very basis of colonialism, the colonizing power needed to facilitate good transport and communication network. From the onset, the colonial authorities had recognized that the indigenous means of transportation could not promote and sustain an expanding market economy (Njoku, 2014: 195). Lord Lugard attested to the opinion of the colonial administration when he unequivocally stated that the material development of Africa may be summarized in one word – Transport (Lugard, 1923:5). Indeed, improving and modernizing transportation in Africa especially railways, roads and waterways, became the focal projects of governments. Besides, without efficient transport system in place, the colonial idea would have been dead on arrival considering the rapidly increasing trade, as well as to facilitate governance and for ease of movement of officials from one place to another.

However, the basis for the construction of roads, railways, waterways and bridges were self-serving because it was primarily to enhance the evacuation of primary produce from the hinterland to the coast for onward shipment abroad. These roads, bridges and railways were selectively constructed to connecting areas of economic interest like the coal deposit at Enugu and palm oil zone of the East, cocoa belt of the West and cotton zone of Northern Nigeria, for example. As such, there were no roads connecting different colonies and different parts of same

colony in a manner that made sense with regards to Africa needs and development. Places that were not productive of export goods were neglected, even if they were very productive of domestic staples (Njoku, 2014:198). As a result, important Africa precolonial cities that were by-passes by railroads drastically declined. Such cities like Sokoto, Ijebu-Ode, Nembe, Bonny and Calabar for example. Thus, the northern part of Kenya or the South of Sudan had little to export, and as such these places were simply ignored by the colonialists with regard to means of transportation (Rodney, 1972:227).

While the production of cash crops tremendously enriched Europe, it bastardized the African economy. Describing the trend in Mozambique, Gabriel Mautio Nantombo therefore remarked that:

When the company came to exploit our region, everyone was force to cultivate one field of cotton... The time of cotton growing was a time of great poverty, because we could only produce cotton. The people didn't want to; they knew cotton is the mother of poverty, but the company was protected by government. We knew that anyone who refused to grow it would be sent to the plantations in Sao Tome where he would work without any pay at all. So as not to leave the family and the children to suffer alone, we had to grow cotton (cited in Imbua et al, 2017:167).

The aforementioned economic situation largely explains, the over-dependence on one or two cash crops which became the hallmark of the colonial economic policy explains the monolithic economy of postcolonial African states, as a colonial legacy. In Senegal and Gambia, groundnut accounted for 85% to 90% of foreign exchange, for example. The point to be made here is that, since these cash crops were produce at the expense of food crops for the populace, starvation and malnutrition was the end result.

In Nigeria, for instance, Asuquo Anwana observed that as at 1951 there were reports of 51% of the children in Northern region died before they reach age six while about 70% of all the children admitted in the hospital in the Eastern region were found to be suffering from malnutrition (Anwana as cited in Imbua et al, 2017: 168). This is because colonialism created

conditions which led to chronic undernourishment and deterioration in the physique and health of the African peoples. It is true African diets was diverse and nutritious in the precolonial period than was possible under capitalist pressures in the colonial era. In fact, kwashiorkor and other diseases ravaged Africa like wild fire during the colonial period.

It is remarkable to note that the colonizers were not interested in making the gains of industrial Europe on their African colonies; in the development of agriculture and industrialization despite the huge agricultural produce, exported to feed European industries as the much – needed raw materials. Throughout the colonial enterprise, the hoe and machete remained the dominant agricultural implements. Truly, mechanization was not extended to Africans, the farmers remained at zero-sum technology in the improvement of agricultural tools and methods, as a matter of colonial policy. Walter Rodney describes this colonial attitude as “an inescapable feature of colonialism as a whole, based on the understanding that the international division of labour aimed at skills in the metropolises and the low-level manpower in the dependencies (Rodney, 1972:240). Colonialism therefore deprived Africans the avenue of not only improving their indigenous skills and technologies but also tapping from modern industrial and agricultural techniques, which is factored as one of the bane to food production in Africa.

In order to perpetuate or facilitate colonial exploitation, the patterns of production, specialization and consumption in the dependencies were changed. During the period underscored, African colonies were compelled to sell their products only to Europe, whereas in the precolonial era, European merchants exchange European goods for African goods, before the monetization of the economy. The colonies were proscribed by law from processing their own raw materials into finished goods. Incidentally, the realization of the cultivation of cash crops for European factories was elevated and encourage above the production of food crops for the domestic population. This is to ensure ready markets for manufactured imports from the metropolises, the colonial subjects were programmed and subjected to consume imported goods and to export their raw materials. This is aptly captured by Bade Onimode when he posited that:

This is the source of the profound disarticulation and distortion and paradox of the colonial and post – colonial economy to this day: it produces what it does not consume (cash crops) and consume what it does not produce (manufactured goods).

Continuing further he averred that:

It was on these perverse pillars that the colonial regimes erected a global system of unequal capitalist development between the metropolises and Africa (Onimode, 1985: 245).

This was how, according to Rodney, Europe underdeveloped Africa and this is what Andre Frank described how, the development of underdevelopment was manifested in Latin America. This is that the resources and the surplus of the dependencies were plundered or pillaged systematically for the development of the metropolises. African colonies became underdeveloped while the metropolises developed tremendously even beyond the capacity of their domestic economies.

It is however seen that whatever benefits Africa might be said to have derived from colonialism were mere coincident rather than planned effort. Arguably, such benefits are accidental following the exploitation of Africa by the colonialists. The summary truth is that, without the establishment of those colonial pillars driven by profit motive as aforementioned, the colonial project would have ended in disarray.

Neocolonialism, the Debt Problem and Food Crisis

There can be no justification that Africa's colonial past is still haunting her even after more than a half century of political independence by most states in the African continent, is its state of neocolonial present condition. This is that the development of the West, had been made possible by the subordination and exploitation of the former colonies, at the expense of the periphery's stagnation and impoverishment, and continued to the present.

In this manner, European colonialist's repackaged indigenous African economies increasingly dependent on the global capitalist system, which Professor Adiele Afigbo convincingly described as being an economic umbilical cord that links Africa to Europe. According to Afigbo, umbilical cord means that:

In the cosmos of natural existence, an umbilical cord is a device through which an underdeveloped or developing entity is fed by a more fully developed parent. But in man-made cosmos of socio-cultural relationships, an umbilical cord is a device through which

the undeveloped feeds the more fully developed-here, through which the fully developed West drew nourishment from the underdeveloped or developing Africa (Afigbo, 2009: 706-7).

Also, colonialism inculcated a culture of exploitation and repatriation of capital in Africa. Thus, independence underpins indigenous exploitation of the masses of Africa by “pirates in power”, to recalibrate Basil Davidson’s popular phrase. These African pirates unarguably do not only sell their nation’s resources; they also lodge the proceeds in their personal Swiss accounts abroad (Njoku, 2014: XIV)

To stress this contemporary trend of exploitation, there are claims that Africa was better off under colonial rule and that the panacea to its predicament is re-colonization rather than foreign aid. This is that Africa’s neocolonial leaders failed to live up to the promises of independence. This broadly suggests that the continent’s indigenous leaders have been exploiting their poor masses much more brutally and more mindlessly than the European colonizers did. Increasingly however, the narrative is changing from how Europe underdeveloped Africa to how Africans are underdeveloping Africa.

We note however that what Africa went through during colonial rule is nothing to them, so far as their interests are accommodated in the pillage and exploitation. Thus, contemporary neocolonialism in Africa was graphically expressed by a former President of Gabon, Monsieur Leon M’ba that “Gabon is independent but between Gabon and France nothing has changed; everything goes on as before” (Fanon, 1968:52) eloquently expresses the reality in most African nations berates Africa leadership style and agenda. This trapping of a neocolonial agenda is elegantly expressed by Eskor Toyo thus:

The benefit of neocolonialism to the imperialists is that they are able to continue the exploitation of the country by operating under the umbrella of a so-called “national” government. The benefit of neocolonialism to the indigenous bourgeoisie is that they thus acquire a powerful economic, military and political ally for their own participation in the exploitation of the people and country (Toyo, 2000:13).

The nexus is that, the international division of labour and colonialism which were used to enforce it are the historical causes of food crisis. This is so because the colonialists have frustrated the nurturing of vibrant indigenous economics as a way of generating secure livelihoods, food security, community integration, political accountability etc. After destabilizing Africa they utilized dimensions to reap the economic benefits from their former colonies when the latter were under colonial rule. Neocolonialism best illustrates the umbilical cord used by the former colonial powers to control the economy and ultimately the political life of the former colonies. Thus scholars articulate the methods used by this hydra-headed monster are varied and complex, depending on the circumstance (Nodari, 1981:12; Anokari, 1997:9). France, for instance grants financial assistance to some of her former African colonies to enable them balance their budgets. At other times, French military personnel garrison the capital of the former colonies. Clearly such military presence are usually in response to joint defense pacts. In all, the tendency is to ensure the survival of those allies in power.

In light of this, Claude Ake studiously writes neocolonialism operate through a local ruling comprador or class (Ake, 1975). Of course, without a willing indigenous bourgeoisie, neocolonialism would have been dead on arrival. Through this and other media of the local compradors that neocolonialism operates and in most cases, reinforcing location of the domestic economy within dictates of the global economic system, make African domestic economies vulnerable. Couples with diverse factors ranging from policy misdirection to discontinuities especially agricultural plans and implementations, corruption, weak institutions, and wars, among others.

Africa and other third world countries are deeply indebted to IMF and the World Bank, and foreign governments. For, at the center of the global economic system lies insignificant, an unequal trade and credit facility that is increasingly impoverishing Africa as a member continent of the global economy. And the prices of primary goods have been fluctuating in the global market thus depleting the capacity for foreign exchange earnings of Africa and others. However, to make up for the deficit, they had to borrow from IMF, World Bank, and foreign governments and to pay interest on the existing loans. This would then soar the amount of their total indebtedness.

Furthermore, the advanced economies used protectionist measures to prevent goods from Africa from getting into their countries. This is in addition with heavily subsidized agro-sector in the developed economies. This is that subsidies stifle agricultural development in poor countries and are considered unfair, because they prevent Africa from benefitting from liberalized global markets by removing their comparative advantage over advanced economies (News Africa, 2002:14). Meanwhile, the monies they borrowed to set up the factories and interest accruing from the monies needed to be paid, and since they could not pay debts by exporting manufactured goods they had to export much more quantity of primary products. In fact, for African countries to maintain the status quo they need to export more as well as increase the acreage under cultivation. This in effect is the realization neglecting domestic food production as resources were deployed from the production of domestic food staples to the production of exportable products. Calibrating this cyclical life of Africa and other third world countries Rene Dumont notes to service the debts, more primary products need to be exported. Conversely, to export more primary products, more lands, labour and other resources have to be diverted from the production of domestic food staples. There is accordingly a vicious circle linking the development policy of the Third World countries, especially Africa their debt problem and food crisis (Dumont, 1988:7).

Also that, with poor technology Africa cannot sell what it does not produce. Truly, Africa is wallowing in globalization. Globalization emphasizes liberalization of finance, trade, technology; and a globally packaged culture. Africa lacks all these. This suggests that Africa may not have items to share in the benefits of globalization. This precarious situation is made worse by the World Trade Organization, which has placed embargo on export of intellectual property and has called for the removal of subsidies in agriculture really puts Africa in more troubled waters.

Conclusion

It has been argued in this historical exercise that, Africa is natural resource rich but also the most exploited and brutally dehumanized peoples on the face of the earth. The explanation of this historical process of external interactions that culminated into colonialism, neocolonialism, dependency, and globalization, as well as the role of the African ruling elite, is blamed on Africa's underdevelopment. This however is increasingly, changing the narrative from how

Europe underdeveloped Africa to how Africans are underdeveloping Africa. Couples with cash crops elevation and encouragement above the production of food crops to feed the domestic population and programmed to consume imported goods (manufactures) they did not produce and produce what they did not consume (raw materials), unequal exchange, debt problem and leadership failure, the paper argued lies the core of Africa's food crisis.

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